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Slag valorization symposium, 18-20th April 2023

Fuming process of zinc rich slags by hydrogen injection

Gunnar Hovestadt, Prof. Bernd Friedrich

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- ❑ Molten state reduction of copper slag together with Aurubis AG and Linde AG
- ❑ Copper slags as raw material (primary and secondary)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 958307

Advantages

- CO₂-neutral reduction fuming process
- Faster kinetics than CH₄ or coal injection
- More selective reduction process

Challenge

- ❖ Low spec. reduction amount
(mol O removed/m³ reductant injected)

Products

- ❑ Heavy metal „free“ slag
- ❑ Zn, Pb flue dust
- ❑ Cu based alloy

➤ Fuming of elements (Zn, Pb) better with higher gas volume

$$k = \frac{p_{Zn} \cdot p_{H_2O}}{a_{ZnO} \cdot p_{H_2}}$$

➤ Low influence on reduction equilibrium

- Depends on H₂/H₂O ratio

$$k = \frac{a_{Cu}^2 \cdot p_{H_2O}}{a_{Cu_2O} \cdot p_{H_2}}$$

Setup

- Resistant heated furnace
- $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ based lining
- Al_2O_3 sintered lance
- MFCs for gas mixing and controlling

Parameters

- 1300 °C temperature
- Flow rates 0.5 – 2.0 l/min
- H_2 -concentration 25 – 100 vol.%
- 1500 g input mass
- Fixed H_2 amount of 90 l
- ❑ Slag from secondary copper smelter

	FeO	SiO ₂	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃	Cu ₂ O	ZnO	PbO	NiO	SnO ₂	Rest
wt.%	41.6	19.6	3.9	8.5	1.2	5.0	0.27	0.15	0.2	18.4

Primary Cu-slag < 1 wt.% ZnO in proceedings

- Zinc can be fumed off to 0.45 wt.%
- Copper content could be reduced to 0.32 wt.% Cu
 - Influence of H₂-concentration behaves like simulation
 - ❖ No significant iron reduction

H₂ concentration (25, 50, 75 % H₂)

- No kinetic trend on fuming
- Influence on the reduction

H₂ amount / turbulence (0.5, 1.0, 1.5 l/min H₂)

- Influence on fuming and reduction
- Reduction of metals is strongly influenced by the hydrogen amount added
- Fuming is more influenced by amount of gas

- Fuming of Zinc behaves like simulation
 - Same slopes and values
- Reduction of other oxides worse than simulation
 - Equilibrium not reached
- Difference between elements being fumed off and reduced into a metal phase

Yield of hydrogen

- Spec. H₂ amount increasing
- $$\eta = \frac{n(O \text{ removed from } Cu_2O, ZnO, NiO, PbO, SnO_2)}{n(H_2)}$$
 - H₂ yield in best case 31 %

Conclusion

- Simulation and experiments have same trends
 - Higher injection volume leads to better fuming
 - Reduction faster with higher H₂-concentration/amount
- Fuming process could be performed selectively (low iron reduction)
- Most metals could be removed

Outlook

- Scale up of experiments (500 kg)
 - Production of metal and flue dust
- Influence of H₂/H₂O ratios
- Looping of H₂-offgas

Thank you for your attention!

M.Braun

HARARE

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